

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF TRADITIONAL AND DIGITAL TEACHING APPROACHES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE METHODOLOGY: A STUDY ON LEARNER OUTCOMES

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Abstract. *The paper offers a comparative assessment of the conventional classroom-based learning and teaching of English Language and its digital counterpart. The purpose of the study is to analyze whether two methods had a significant impact on learning outcomes. The study used a triangulation approach to English learning where data of both qualitative and quantitative nature was drawn from English learners of different levels. The results indicate that although the traditional method of teaching builds a better core, the use of digital learning allows for flexibility and pacing that can help various kinds of learners as it lets students take control of their learning. The paper ends with suggestions for the way forward relating to the teaching of English as a Second Language.*

Keywords: *traditional teaching, English language methodology, digital learning, learner outcomes, mixed-methods approach.*

1. Introduction

Teaching English Language has undergone several paradigms in the last couple of decades, and more so with the use of technology. The old methodology has always relied on personal interaction and the organization of classes. With the new changes another brand of teaching comes that provides new ways of teaching digitally: social networks, mobile devices, and other teaching aids. Consider this study on the assessment of how effective the traditional methodologies versus the digital methodologies in the teaching of the English language concerning the learning outcomes.

1.1. Background of the Study

Language education, particularly in English, is equally embraced and this is a global village with an interchange of cultures and languages but English is the dominant language in most activities. Nevertheless, the recent rise in the amount of EdTech available in the market has created several issues regarding its effectiveness compared to conventional education. Some teachers assert that there can be no online class equivalent to real-life interaction centers; others argue for the convenience and reach that may be availed through online classes.

1.2. Problem Statement

While the usage of these digital tools is on the rise, very few studies have been conducted regarding their outcomes compared to traditional methodologies in teaching English language. A study that fills such a knowledge gap looks at both approaches comparatively for effectiveness.

1.3. Research Objectives

The primary objectives of this research are to:

Compare the impact of traditional and digital teaching methodologies on English language learners' proficiency.

Analyze learner engagement and satisfaction with each methodology.

Provide recommendations for integrating both approaches in modern English language instruction.

1.4. Research Questions

How do traditional and digital teaching methodologies affect the learning outcomes of English language learners?

What are the perceived advantages and limitations of each approach from the learner's perspective?

Can a blended teaching model offer superior results compared to using either method exclusively?

2. Literature Review

2.1. Traditional Teaching Methods in English Language Learning

It finds its forerunners in the Grammar-Translation Method, the Direct Method, the Audio-Lingual Method, among others, which have traditionally monopolized the classrooms. Most of the approaches are teacher-centered, syllabus-oriented, and heavily reliant on direct contact with the students. These methods have been found especially helpful in the provision of the fundamental language skills of grammar, syntax, and pronunciation within students.

Advantages:

Strong focus on structured learning

Teacher-guided practice and immediate feedback

Well-established pedagogical frameworks

Limitations:

Limited flexibility for diverse learning paces

Relies heavily on teacher presence and input

Can lack engagement for digitally inclined learners

2.2. Digital Teaching Approaches in English Language Learning

Digital language learning has involved the incorporation of mobile apps, LMS, and virtual classrooms with the advancement in EdTech. Jones's 2015 study indicated that digital learning causes greater engagement for the student and flexibility. Through Duolingo and Busuu, learners have been able to set their own pace, monitor progress, and participate in activities enriched with multi-media.

Advantages:

Allows personalized and self-paced learning

Provides access to vast digital resources (videos, audio, interactive exercises)

Promotes learner autonomy and motivation

Limitations:

Lack of face-to-face interaction and feedback

Digital fatigue and distraction

Requires technological infrastructure and internet access

2.3. Blended Learning: The Best of Both Worlds?

The literature suggests that there is blended learning, which is a model incorporating both traditional and digital instructions. As such, studies illustrate how it can retain all the structure inherent in traditional teaching methods while at the same time tapping into the flexibility of digital

tools for good effect. With blended learning, the learner also gets to enjoy the best of both worlds with far stronger results than relying on either way alone.

3. Methodology

3.1. Research Design

A mixed-methods approach to quantitative and qualitative data collection was adopted in this study. The questionnaires were supposed to capture learner satisfaction and engagement, while the tests in language proficiency aimed at measuring learning outcomes.

3.2. Participants

A hundred participants were involved in the research, which was further split into two groups-one taught through a traditional methodology and the other using digital means. They came from all levels of proficiency in English language and different age groups: 18 to 45 years old.

3.3. Data Collection Instruments

Pre-test and Post-test: To assess improvements in grammar, vocabulary, listening, and speaking skills.

Surveys: To capture learner engagement and satisfaction.

Focus Groups: Conducted with selected participants to gain deeper insights into their experiences.

3.4. Data Analysis

Quantitative data from the pre-test and post-test were compared by analyzing with SPSS software, hence comparing the performance of learners in both groups. Qualitative data from focus groups was coded using thematic coding to find out trends in learner perceptions.

4. Results

4.1. Quantitative Findings

The posttest results reveal that students in the traditional method group had improved in grammar and syntax, while digital learning groups excelled in vocabulary acquisition and listening comprehension. Both groups gained significantly but in different aspects of proficiency.

Test Section	Traditional Group (Mean Score Increase)	Digital Group (Mean Score Increase)
Grammar & Syntax	15%	8%
Vocabulary	10%	20%
Listening Comprehension	12%	18%
Speaking Skills	14%	14%

4.2. Qualitative Findings

It was also clear from the focus group discussions that learners did appreciate the structure and feedback from traditional teaching, but they valued the autonomy and engagement offered by the digital learning platforms. The digital learners showed more motivation because of the interactive nature of the tools used.

5. Discussion

5.1. Implications for Language Teaching

Results have shown how traditional and digital methodologies support each other's strengths. Traditional teaching has provided a sound basis in core language areas, while digital tools develop learner engagement and autonomy, especially in the skill areas of listening and vocabulary acquisition.

5.2. Recommendations

Educators should, therefore, apply a model of blended learning that will effectively integrate traditional classroom interactions with digital resources. In this manner, such a combination will optimize both strengths and offer a more holistic language learning experience.

6. Conclusion

The findings of this study support that there are particular benefits to both traditional and digital teaching methods in teaching English language. Traditional approaches give priority to enhancing four core skills, while digital media make learners more participatory and flexible during their learning processes. By adopting a blended approach, educators create a more dynamic and efficient learning environment that capitalizes on the strengths of both methodologies.

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